

Kinetics of the Decarboxylation of Methylmalonic Acid in Some Solvents

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Decarboxylation kinetics of methylmalonic acid has been followed in several solvents by measuring volumes of carbon dioxide gas produced at various intervals of time. The kinetics was observed to follow a first order rate law in the following solvents, namely ethylene glycol, propane-1,2-diol 1,3-butane diol, polyethylene glycol and polypropylene glycol. The activation parameters, namely enthalpy of activation $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and entropy of activation $\Delta S^\ddagger$ were evaluated in all these solvents from the linear plot of $\ln(k_r/T)$ vs $1/T$. A plot of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ against $\Delta S^\ddagger$ results in two parallel straight lines, one for alkane diols and the other for diethylene-, polyethylene-, and polypropylene glycols.

In course of our investigations into the decarboxylation kinetics of malonic acid¹, it was observed that the alkane diols and diethylene-, polyethylene- and polypropylene glycols form two categories of solvents, in so far as the kinetic data fall on two straight lines having the same isokinetic temperature, when we plot the enthalpy of activation, $\Delta H^\ddagger$ against the entropy of activation, $\Delta S^\ddagger$. In further support to the existence of isokinetic temperature², we herein report our studies on the decarboxylation of methylmalonic acid in the solvents as a function of temperature.

Experimental

Materials: Methyl malonic acid, white crystalline solid (Fluka) was used without further purification.

Ethylene glycol, pfizer, India was used after distilling twice under reduced pressure. The solvents polyethylene glycol- 400 B. D. H. (England), 1, 3-Butane diol, (Fluka), propane-1, 2-diol B. D. H. ; diethylene glycol B. D. H. (England) and polypropylene glycol-425 Koch-Light (England) were used without further purification.

Rates were determined by collecting CO_2 gas in a gas burette over an aqueous solution prepared by mixing 20% by weight of sodium sulphate and 5% by volume of sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4) coloured with methyl red^{3,4}. Temperature was controlled in a thermostat within $\pm 0.2^\circ$. Heavy grade liquid paraffin was used as the bath liquid. The reaction flask was attached by a light stand to a vibrating plate, resulting in constant and rapid stirring of the reaction mixture.

The gas burette was surrounded by a wider Jacket through which water at room temperature

was circulated. In each run the amount of methyl malonic acid was about 0.105 gm in 25 cc of the solvent which were previously saturated with dry carbon dioxide gas.

Results and Discussion

As with malonic acid, methylmalonic acid undergoes first order decarboxylation in all these solvents in the temperature range 120° - 145° . A plot of $\log(V_\infty - V_t)$ against time, t , produced a straight line for nearly 75% of the decarboxylation process, the volumes of carbon dioxide collected at 't' and after the reaction is completed being V_t and V_∞ respectively. The first order rate constants k_r were then determined from the slopes of the linear plots and these are given in Table 1. In polyethylene- and polypropylene glycols, the decarboxylation proceeds relatively slowly at any temperature between 120° - 145° .

TABLE 1—FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT FOR DECARBOXYLATION OF METHYLMALONIC ACID

Solvents	Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)			
	120	130	140	145
1. Ethylene glycol	3.8	8.8	15.5	18.7
2. 1,3-Butane diol	4.1	12.3	14.7	24.0
3. Propane-1,2-diol	4.2	7.1	14.9	17.9
4. Diethylene glycol	4.1	6.2	9.9	13.9
5. Polyethylene glycol	2.1	4.3	8.9	13.7
6. Polypropylene glycol	2.2	4.7	7.3	10.5

It was also observed that a plot of $\ln(k_r/T)$ against $1/T$ is linear between 120° - 145° for all the solvents included in this investigation. Based on the equation,

$$k_r = \frac{kT}{h} \exp(-\Delta H^\ddagger/RT) \exp(\Delta S^\ddagger/R)$$

where k and h are Boltzmann's constant and Planck's

constant respectively. We evaluated from the-slopes and intercepts, the values of the enthalpy of activation, $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and entropy of activation, $\Delta S^\ddagger$.

In Table 2, we compare the thermodynamic parameters, $\Delta H^\ddagger$; $\Delta S^\ddagger$ and $\Delta F^\ddagger_{135^\circ}$. The values of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ are therefore average over the temperature range studied, but $\Delta F^\ddagger_{135^\circ}$ is the free energy of activation for the decarboxylation process in the solvents at 135° which is calculated from the relation,

$$\Delta F^\ddagger = \Delta H^\ddagger - T\Delta S^\ddagger$$

In Table 2, we see that $\Delta F^\ddagger_{135^\circ}$ clearly clusters around two values, for ethylene glycol, propane-1,2-diol and 1,3-butane diol, the values are very close to one another, i.e., 29.7; 29.7 and 29.6 K cal mole⁻¹ respectively, while for diethylene-, polyethylene- and

TABLE 2—DECARBOXYLATION OF METHYLMALONIC ACID IN VARIOUS SOLVENTS: THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Solvents	Enthalpy of activation $\Delta H^\ddagger$ (K cal/mole)	Entropy activation $\Delta S^\ddagger$ cal deg ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹	Free Energy $\Delta F^\ddagger_{135^\circ}$ K cal mole ⁻¹
1. Ethylene glycol	21.4	-20.3	29.7
2. 1,3-Butane diol	22.4	-17.5	29.6
3. Propane-1,2-diol	17.9	-28.8	29.7
4. Diethylene glycol	15.2	-35.9	30.0
5. Polyethylene glycol-400	25.4	-11.4	30.1
6. Polypropylene glycol-425	20.5	-23.5	30.1

polypropylene glycols the values are, 30.0; 30.1 and 30.1 respectively.

Leffler⁴ believes that in the case of solvents of the same type, a considerable increase in steric hindrance may result in an increase in the enthalpy of activation and a decrease in the entropy of activation. Although the rate constants are generally less in polyethylene glycol and polypropylene glycol, (Table 1) we do not observe a systematic variation of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ in going from one solvent to another.

But it is worth noting that the $\Delta F^\ddagger_{135^\circ}$ the free energy of activation for the decarboxylate process at 135° , distinguishes the solvents into two categories; for alkane diols $\Delta F^\ddagger_{135^\circ}$ is 29.7 K cal mole⁻¹ (average), while for diethylene-, polyethylene- and polypropylene glycol $\Delta F^\ddagger_{135^\circ}$ is 30.1 K cal mole⁻¹ (average).

In Figs. 1 and 2, we have plotted $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ for the decarboxylation reaction of malonic acid¹ and

Fig. 1. $\Delta H^\ddagger$ vs $\Delta S^\ddagger$ plot for the decarboxylation of methylmalonic acid in some solvents.

○ : refers to decarboxylation in ethylene glycol, propane-1,2-diol and 1,3-butane diol.

⊗ : refers to decarboxylation in diethylene glycol, polyethylene glycol and polypropylene glycol.

Fig. 2. $\Delta H^\ddagger$ vs $\Delta S^\ddagger$ plot for the decarboxylation of malonic acid in some solvents.

○ : refers to decarboxylation in ethylene glycol, propane-1,2-diol and 1,3-butane diol.

⊗ : refers to decarboxylation in diethylene glycol, polyethylene glycol and polypropylene glycol.

methylmalonic acid in the various solvents. For each of the acids, we get two parallel straight lines, one for the alkane diols and the other for diethylene-, polyethylene- and polypropylene glycols.

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